

ترجمة رسالة الأستاذة (نورا موير) موجهة الى نوري جعفر بخصوص المؤتمر الدولي لرعاية
الموهوبين العاشر في توريننتو

إلى: الدكتور نوري جعفر
من: لجنة مقترحات المؤتمر الدولي

عزيزي الدكتور جعفر،
أرفق لك طياً إستمارتي المقترح والتسجيل الخاصتين بالمؤتمر العالمي العاشر. يرجى ملاحظة أن
الموعد النهائي لتقديم مقترحات العروض البحثية هو الحادي والثلاثين من كانون الأول، ١٩٩٢.

شكراً لإهتمامكم.

المخلصة

نوراه موير

To: Dr. Nouri Jaffar

From: World Conference Proposal

Dear Dr. Jaffar;

Please find enclosed proposal and registration forms for the 10th World
Conference. Please note that the submission deadline for proposals for
presentation to December, 31st, 1992

Thank you for your interest.

Sincerely,

Norah Moier/ cc

Faculty of Education

University of Toronto

To DR. Nouri Jaffa Date December 3/92
Re World Conference Proposal

Dear Dr. Jaffa:

Please find enclosed proposal and registration forms for the 10th World Conference. Please note that the submission deadline for proposals for presentations has been extended to December 31, 1992

Thank you for your interest.

Sincerely,
Norah Mair/cc

A GIFTED GLOBE

10TH WORLD CONGRESS ON GIFTED AND TALENTED EDUCATION

TORONTO • AUGUST 8-12 • 1993

CONGRESS CONTENT: THE WHO'S WHO OF GIFTED EDUCATION
INTERNATIONAL BENCHMARKS IN EXCELLENCE:
TEACHING – SCHOLARSHIP – RESEARCH
INTERNATIONAL EXPERTS / INNOVATORS
THE XYZ OF CLASSROOM PRACTICE
THE Ps & Qs OF PARENTING
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SPECIAL FEATURES: (a) STRANDS ON – Instruction in sciences, mathematics, the arts; policy; research; creativity; global education; teacher development; technology/communication; space education; multiculturalism; disadvantaged; disabled; gifted and regular education; earth and environment; multidimensional approaches...

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OPPORTUNITIES:**

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